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Preparation, characterization and application of core-shell Fe₃O₄@MAPTMS@PAA@Triazole@Cu(I) nano-composite as a magnetically separable and highly efficient catalyst for selective oxidation of aromatic alcohols using hydrogen peroxide

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Abstract

The poly(acrylic acid) was functionalized with 1,2,3- triazole ring as chelate ligand and used for the modification of the surface of magnetic nanoparticles coated with silica layer to provide Fe₃O₄@MAPTMS@PAA@Triazole. Afterwards, copper chloride (I) was introduced to the aforementioned prepared core-shell for the preparation of Fe₃O₄@MAPTMS@PAA@Triazole@Cu(I). This nano-composite was fully characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), microanalysis, energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and FT-IR spectroscopy. The catalytic activity of the above-mentioned composite was examined in the selective oxidation of differently substituted benzyl alcohols using hydrogen peroxide as a commercially available and environmentally

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benign oxidant in acetonitrile at 60 °C, to obtain the corresponding aldehydes and ketones, selectively in high yields. Mild reaction conditions, ease of catalyst separation using an external magnet bar, short reaction time, and high conversions in the presence of low loading of catalyst were merits for the use this novel catalyst.

Keywords: Alcohol, Selective oxidation, Hydrogen peroxide, Magnetically separable, Triazole